

6TH EDITION

*THE INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE*

COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY

TÎRGU MUREȘ

24-25 OCTOBER 2020

COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY 6

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CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

SATURDAY- 24 OCTOBER 2020

"Dimitrie Cantemir" University, Tîrgu Mureş

8⁰⁰ - 10⁰⁰ - Registration – Room A23

10⁰⁰ - 11⁰⁰ - Welcome and Opening – Room A22

11⁰⁰ - 13⁰⁰ – Paper Presentations on Sections:

- **Literature – Room A22**
- **Language and Discourse – Room A24**
- **Communication, Journalism, Education Sciences, Psychology and Sociology - Room A25**
- **History, Political Sciences, International Relations – Room A27**
- **Social Sciences – Room A28**

13⁰⁰ - 14⁰⁰ – Lunch

14⁰⁰ - 18⁰⁰ - Paper Presentations on Sections

18⁰⁰ - Gratulatory Dinner

The conference is organised in partnership by:

**"Alpha" Institute for Multicultural Studies
"Gh. Şincai" Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities
"Dimitrie Cantemir" University of Tîrgu Mureş**

COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY 6

SUNDAY – 25 OCTOBER 2020

Sightseeing: cultural objectives in the Mureş county.

A WORD FROM THE PRESIDENT OF THE CONFERENCE

Dear Guests,

Having established a certain tradition in the recent years, the International Conference *COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY* (now at its 6th edition) intends to unite emerging scholars, as well as prestigious researchers from different fields of radical relevance for the contemporary society, a society that is supposed to secure its future not only on the economic and ecological level, but also on the spiritual one. Literature, the cultural discourses as well as the arts gain new connections and dimensions through fundamental changes and structural progress, so that the social end-results of education and research becomes extremely important. It is a fact that in our postmodern times, we live in a society of knowledge, from which we benefit directly in our everyday life, but to the risks and dangers of which we are at the same time exposed. *Non scholae sed vitae discimus* (*We do not learn for the school, but for life*) becomes a creed that every academic institution has to put into practice by means of its activities. It is essential that the path between education and research is very short, especially in academic systems. Research generates new knowledge, creates a favourable atmosphere for change, and provides people with information and data which help them to become aware of the mysteries of the universe and to make the most of their activity in all fields of knowledge. In this interesting and captivating century, to the noble mission of educating the younger generations we must also add the fruit of the efforts in research, materialized in interesting works and papers, together with ideas generated by the creative ability which ennobles the personality of the academic.

COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY 6

I wish to express my hope that this scientific event will take place under the most favourable auspices and that it will represent a remarkable starting point for further evolution and development in the field of knowledge. Let this international conference provide a good opportunity for us to gain and transfer knowledge, to generate new theories in the world of science – essential aspirations of any contemporary research.

Prof. IULIAN BOLDEA, PhD
President of the *CCI 6* Conference

SATURDAY – 24 OCTOBER 2020

LITERATURE I – Room: A22

Moderators: Prof. Iulian Boldea, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Assoc. Prof. Nicoleta Călina, PhD, University of Craiova; Assoc. Prof. Dumitru-Mircea Buda, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș.

1. Iulian Boldea, Prof., PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș, *IOAN ALEXANDRU - BETWEEN VITALISM AND SPIRITUALITY*
2. Ion Popescu-Brădiceni, Prof. PhD, „Constantin Brâncuși” University of Târgu Jiu, *A VERY SHORT INTRODUCTION IN CONTEMPORARY ROMANIAN POETRY (II)*
3. Yolanda-Mirela Catelly, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Politehnica University of Bucharest, *GENRE ANALYSIS IN ADVERTISING CREATION - SYNERGIC TRENDS TODAY*
4. Delia-Anamaria Răchișan, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Baia Mare Northern University Center, *STRIGOI – INTERDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVE*
5. Dorina Chiș-Toia, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Eftimie Murgu” University of Reșița, *FROM THE LITTLE PRINCE TO THE YOUNG PRINCE*
6. Angela Stănescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Valahia” University of Târgoviște, *THE ART OF (UN)FORGETTING REVISITED: KAZUO ISHIGURO’S THE BURIED GIANT*
7. Lavinia Bănică, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Pitești, *MEANINGS OF THE SEARCH FOR LOVE IN CREANGA DE AUR BY MIHAIL SADOVEANU*

SATURDAY – 24 OCTOBER 2020

LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE – Room: A24

Moderators: Prof. Doina Butiurca, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Assoc. Prof. Carmen Neamțu, PhD, "Aurel Vlaicu" University of Arad; Assoc. Prof. Adela Marinela Stancu, University of Craiova

1. Doina Butiurca, Prof. PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș, *LINGUISTIC STRATEGIES OF ON-LINE COMMUNICATION*
2. Mirela-Cristina Pop, Prof. PhD, Politehnica University of Timișoara, Mihaela Popescu, PhD Student, West University of Timișoara, *DU FRANÇAIS DE SPECIALITE AU FRANÇAIS PROFESSIONNEL : ESSAI DE DEFINITION DES CONCEPTS*
3. Alina Balagiu, Assoc. Prof. PhD, „Mircea cel Bătrân” Naval Academy, Constanța, *ONLINE COURSE FOR MARINE ENGINEERING – FEEDBACK*
4. Anca-Mariana Pegulescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romanian Academy, *NUANCES CONVEYED BY COMMUNICATIVE STRATEGIES IN PROVERBIAL SOCIAL STRUCTURES*
5. Carmen Neamțu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Aurel Vlaicu” State University of Arad, *IMAGE-TEXT-CREATIVITY IN THE DISCOURSE OF ADVERTISING. ANALYSIS AND PERSPECTIVES DURING COVID PANDEMIC TIMES*
6. Sorin Guia, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE PALATALIZATION OF LABIAL CONSONANTS IN ROMANIAN DIALECTS*

SATURDAY – 24 OCTOBER 2020

***COMMUNICATION, JOURNALISM, EDUCATION
SCIENCES, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIOLOGY***

Room: A25

Moderators: Prof. Maria-Ana Georgescu, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureş; Prof. Odette Arhip, PhD, Ecological University of Bucharest; Assoc. Prof. Doina David, PhD, "Dimitrie Cantemir" University of Târgu Mureş

1. Maria-Ana Georgescu, Prof. PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureş, *ABANDONMENT AND VIOLENCE AGAINST CHILDREN. THE EVOLUTION OF THE PHENOMENON IN ROMANIA AND IN MUREŞ COUNTY*
2. Cristian Arhip, Assist. Prof., PhD, University of Medicine and Pharmacy „Gr. T. Popa”of Iaşi, Odette Arhip, Prof. PhD, Ecological University of Bucharest, *MYTHOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN ADVERTISING AUTO BRANDS*
3. Camelia Nistor, Prof., PhD, Afiliate Prof., PhD, United International Business Schools, Bruxelles, „Babeş-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION IN BUILDING BRAND REPUTATION*
4. Doina David, Assoc. Prof, PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureş, *COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE VS. CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING SOCIO-HUMAN SCIENCES*
5. Doina David, Assoc. Prof, PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureş, *DIDACTIC APPROACH TO COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN STUDENTS*

SATURDAY – 24 OCTOBER 2020

**HISTORY, POLITICAL SCIENCES, INTERNATIONAL
RELATIONS – Room: A27**

Moderators: Prof. Cornel Sigmirean, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Assoc. Prof. Giordano Altarozzi, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Assoc. Prof. William Bleiziffer, PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca.

1. Cornel Sigmirean, Prof., PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș, *THE FATE OF AN 18th CENTURY INTELLECTUAL: IOAN BUDAI-DELEANU*
2. George Bondor, Prof., PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *TRANSMISSION AS MEDIATION OF LIFE AND CULTURE*
3. Ion M. Tomuș, Prof., PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *ONLINE THEATRE, AN ALTERNATIVE TO THE TRADITIONAL THEATRE SET WITHIN THE CURRENT PANDEMIC CONTEXT*
4. William Bleiziffer, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *DE CULTO DIVINO ET PRESERTIM DE SACRAMENTIS: A SHORT ANALYSIS OF CANONICAL ROOTS OF THE ROMANIAN GREEK-CATHOLIC CHURCH FROM CODEX CANONUM ECCLESIAE ORIENTALIIUM*
5. Adrian-Claudiu Stoica, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University Politehnica of Bucharest, *PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS WITHIN THE EUROPEAN UNION*

COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY 6

6. Giordano Altarozzi, Assoc. Prof., PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș, *THE KINGDOM OF SARDINIA AND THE UNION OF DANUBIAN PRINCIPALITIES*
7. Marius Liviu Telea, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "1 Decembrie 1918" University of Alba Iulia, *THE RESURRECTION OF HELLENISM IN THE ROMAN-BYZANTINE EMPIRE DURING THE REIGN OF EMPEROR JULIAN THE APOSTATE (361-363)*
8. Sorin Bulboacă, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Vasile Goldiș” West University of Arad, *DISAPPEARED MEDIEVAL SETTLEMENTS LOCATED IN THE AREA OF PECICA*
9. Lucretia-Dorina Loghin, Lecturer, PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *QUO VADIS HOMINE? IS MANKIND UNDERGOING A TRANSITION TOWARDS A NON-RELIGIOUS SOCIETY?*
10. Ioana Banaduc, Lecturer, PhD, West University of Timișoara, *THE VITALITY OF THE FABLES. ON MORAL EDUCATION*
11. Mirela Beguni, Lecturer, PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *A SAD MOMENT IN THE HISTORY OF MOLDAVIA: THE RETIREMENT OF VENIAMIN COSTACHI FROM THE METROPOLITAN CHAIR (1842)*
12. Ștefan Lifa, Lecturer, PhD, West University of Timișoara, *INFORMATION FROM LITERARY SOURCES REGARDING LATE ANTIQUITY AND THE FIRST PART OF THE MIDDLE AGES*
13. Monica Meruțiu, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *TERRORIST THREATS IN EUROPE: ANALYSIS ON FRANCE AND BELGIUM*
14. Roxana Marin, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *ON THE ISSUE OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ROMANIA: SOME INTRODUCTORY REMARKS*

COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY 6

15. Florentina Trif, Conservator I., „Ovidius” University of Constanța, *ROMANIA'S CONCERNS REGARDING THE PROTECTION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE*
16. Ion-Daniel Cismașu, Arhivist within the Gorj County Service of National Archives, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *FREDERICH DREXLER AND THE FIRST CERAMICS FACTORY OF TÂRGU JIU DURING THE TIME OF THE ORGANIC REGULATION*
17. Bogdan-Ștefan Cristea, PhD, Romanian Academy, *THE ROMANIAN ACADEMY AND THE SITUATION OF THE ROMANIANS FROM TRANSYLVANIA AND HUNGARY IN 1894*
18. Lisa-Maria Achimescu, PhD, “Carol I” National Defense University, Angela Ioniță, Senior Researcher I, Research Institute for Artificial Intelligence „Mihai Drăgănescu”, Romanian Academy, *THE EMERGENCE OF INTERNATIONAL CYBERSPACE LAW AND THE CONSEQUENCES PERTAINING TO INDIVIDUALS*
19. Dragoș Lucian Curelea, PhD, Sibiu, Daniela Ștefania Curelea, PhD Student, „Cibinium” Technical College, Sibiu & CRIFST Brașov, *ENDEAVOURS OF SOCIAL PEDAGOGY PERFORMED BY ASTRA THROUGH „ASTRA CINEGRAFICĂ” S.A. TRADE COMPANY IN ITS PICTURE THEATRES IN BRAȘOV, CLUJ, ORAVIȚA AND SIBIU (1927-1936)*
20. Florin F Nacu, Scientific Researcher III, PhD, “CS Nicolăescu-Plopșor” Social Humanistic Research Institute, Craiova, Romanian Academy, *TUDOR VLADIMIRESCU AND THE QUESTION OF THE MODERN LAW*
21. Ferencz-Iozsef Truța, Research Assistant, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities of the Romanian Academy, Târgu Mureș, *THE POSSIBLE RE-*

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- OCCURRENCE OF SPANISH FLU IN THE ROMANIAN SPACE (1922-1943). EPISODES OF FEAR*
22. Corina Hațegan, Scientific Resercher, PhD, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities of the Romanian Academy, *THE COMMUNIST REGIME AND THE POST COMMUNIST SOCIAL CHANGES IN THE LAST 30 YEARS IN TODAY’S PUBLIC CONSCIOUSNESS. THE RESULTS OF A SURVEY IN MUREȘ COUNTY (ROMANIA)*
 23. Mihaela Bărbieru, Scientific Researcher III, PhD, „C.S. Nicolăescu-Plopșor” Social Humanistic Research Institute, Craiova, *THE ROMANIAN MULTI-PARTY DURING THE FIRST YEARS FOLLOWING THE REVOLUTION*
 24. Vasile Pleșca, Scientific Researcher III, PhD, „Gh. Zane” Institute of Economic and Social Research, Romanian Academy, Iași, *LIBERAL DEMOCRACY AND ITS EXAMS*
 25. Maria Costea, PhD, “Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences and Humanities of the Romanian Academy, *BRUSSELS’ INITIATIVES AND REACTIONS FACING THE GEOPOLITICAL RECONFIGURATIONS IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE*
 26. Janeta-Maria Iuga, Postdoctoral researcher, Ionela Toda, MA student, West University of Timișoara, *THE OLD SONG - THE COMMUNICATION OF VALUES IN THE TRADITIONAL ROMANIAN VILLAGE*
 27. Constantin Scurtu, PhD, „Regele Ferdinand I” National Military Museum, Constanța, *ASPECTS OF THE EVOLUTION OF THE LOCAL PUBLIC TRANSPORT SERVICE IN ROMANIA*
 28. Gherghina Boda, Scientific Researcher, PhD, habil., curator, „Dacian and Roman Civilization Museum”, *THE MAGAZINE BOABE DE GRÂU ABOUT THE EXHIBITIONS DEDICATED TO CHILDREN AND YOUNG PEOPLE (1930 – 1934)*

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29. Ionuț Horeanu, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE ISSUE OF HISTORICAL EDUCATIONAL REFORM FROM ZELETIN'S POINT OF VIEW*
30. Narcis-Mihai Martiniuc, Research Assistant, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences, Târgu-Mureș, *FRIEDRICH BENESCH: IMPORTANT CONTRIBUTIONS TO AN ANTHROPOLOGY THEOLOGY*
31. Eduard Rusu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *MUSIC OF THE EMBASSYS*
32. Eduard Rusu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE BAGPIPERS AND THE GAMES OF THE PRINCELY COURT*
33. Ciprian Dumitriu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *NEW CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE ORIGIN AND BEGINNING OF THE ACTIVITY OF GRIGORE II GHICA*
34. Mihai Cristian Neagu, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *THE FIRST BATTLE OF THE CRIMEAN WAR-THE BATTLE OF OLTENITA*
35. Laurențiu-Mircea Pascu, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *MARIA DUMITRESCU - A FORGOTTEN TEACHER OF THE SCHOOL OF ARCHIVING. DOCUMENTARY SOURCES AND BIOGRAPHICAL REFERENCES*
36. Codruța Șoroagă, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *EROTIC INCIDENTS AT THE ROMANIAN ROYAL COURT: "THE VĂCĂRESCU BUSINESS"*
37. Cristian-Constantin Lupașcu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE APRIORI OF CULTURE. REASON AND IRRATIONALITY IN ROMANIAN INTERWAR THOUGHT*

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38. Cozmin-Valerian Broșteanu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE CRISIS OF THE ROMAN EMPIRE IN THE LATE LATIN BREVIA TORS*
39. Flavian-Pavel Chilcoș, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *DAMNATIO MEMORIAE OF COMMODUS (180 – 192 C. E.)*
40. Sorin Buzatu, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *MARXISM AND SYNDICALISM IN CONSTANTIN DOBROGEANU-GHEREA AND LUCREȚIU PĂTRĂȘCANU’S VISION*
41. Valeriu-Bogdan Preda, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *COLD WAR CRISES IN THE 1960S: THE SOCIALIST REPUBLIC OF ROMANIA, THE GERMAN DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC AND THEIR INVOLVEMENT IN THE VIETNAM WAR*
42. Gheorghe-Cristian Grecoiu, PhD Student, counselor within the Gorj County Service of National Archives, University of Craiova, *TÂRGU JIU IN THE FIRST DECADE AFTER THE INDEPENDENCE WAR (1878-1888)*

SATURDAY – 24 OCTOBER 2020

SOCIAL SCIENCES – Room: A28

Moderators: Prof. Lucreția Dogaru, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Prof. Petruța Blaga, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Assoc. Prof. Adriana Cîteia, PhD, "Ovidius" University of Constanța

1. Carmen Comaniciu, Prof., PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *PROVISIONS AND EFFECTS ON PUBLIC PROCUREMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SARS-COV 2 PANDEMIC*
2. Lucreția Dogaru, Prof., PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș, *THE EUROPEAN UNION INVOLVEMENT IN NUCLEAR POLICY AND IN THE FIGHT AGAINST CHEMICAL AND BIOLOGICAL WEAPONS*
3. Lucreția Dogaru, Prof., PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș, *ATMOSPHERIC PROTECTION - BETWEEN REALITY, POLICIES AND STRATEGIES*
4. Petruța Blaga, Prof., PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș, *CONSIDERATIONS ON THE IMPORTANCE OF ERGONOMICS IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN WORKPLACES DESIGN*
5. Nicolae Iuga, Prof., PhD, Associate Researcher Gr. I, „Constantin Rădulescu-Motru” Philosophy Institute, Romanian Academy, *THE AMERICANIZATION OF EUROPE?*
6. Laura-Mariana Cismaș, Prof. PhD, West University of Timișoara, Mariana Nagy, Prof. PhD, „Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad, Olimpia-Neliana Tudur, PhD Student,

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GENERAL INFORMATION

Conference Fee: 230 LEI

The fee applies to each participant paper. In the case of papers with multiple authors, each author will pay the value of the fee individually.

Deadline: 5 October 2020

Payment information: *Asociația pentru cultură, multimedia și educație democratică ALPHA*

Bank Account (IBAN): RO59RNCB0188137564490001

Fiscal Code: 32308751

Paper submission - (title, abstract submission) until **25 September 2020**, by email, to:

iulian.boldea@gmail.com

Confirmation - 30 September 2020

A participant may present at most 2 papers as author or co-author, papers that will be published in the Proceedings of the conference. Each paper will be under 12 pages. The presentation time is 15 minutes.

Instructions for Authors:

Paper format: A4, 1,5 space between lines, 20 mm equal margins, justified;

The title will be written in capitals, Times New Roman 14 Bold, Centered, at 50 mm above the text;

The author's name, scientific title and academic affiliation – Times New Roman 12 Bold, under the title, at 2 lines distance;

The abstract – Times New Roman 11, italics, at two lines distance under the author's name, in English;

Five key-words under the abstract, in English (TNR 11);

The text of the paper, at one line below the abstract, Times New Roman 12;

The Bibliography at the end of the paper;

No endnotes (footnotes only); No Page Breaks in the document; All graphic elements set inline with the text.

All papers will be submitted electronically in Microsoft Word 2007 format.

The Book of Proceedings will be sent for evaluation in order to be indexed in Clarivate Analytics Web of Science (ISI).

Full paper submission – DEADLINE:

10 October 2020

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The International Scientific Conference

COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY

6th EDITION

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TÎRGU MUREȘ

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Conference Schedule

SATURDAY – 24 OCTOBER 2020

8⁰⁰-10⁰⁰ - REGISTRATION

10⁰⁰ -11⁰⁰- WELCOME AND OPENING

11⁰⁰ -13⁰⁰ – PAPER PRESENTATIONS ON SECTIONS:

- LITERATURE
- LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE
- COMMUNICATION AND PUBLIC RELATIONS
- JOURNALISM
- HISTORY AND CULTURAL MENTALITIES
- PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION SCIENCE
- POLITICAL SCIENCES, INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS
- SOCIOLOGY
- SOCIAL SCIENCES

13⁰⁰ -15⁰⁰ - LUNCH

15⁰⁰ -18 - PAPER PRESENTATIONS ON SECTIONS

18⁰⁰ - GRATULATORY DINNER

SUNDAY – 25 OCTOBER 2020

SIGHTSEEING: CULTURAL OBJECTIVES IN MUREȘ COUNTY.

Useful information

Accommodation:

Hotel Options	Single Room	Double Rooms	Apartments
Hotel Continental ***			211 LEI
	140 LEI	160 LEI	
Pensiunea Europa ****			240 LEI
	144 LEI	188 LEI	
Hotel Voiajor ***	135 LEI	160 LEI	-
Hotel Week-end **	-	100 LEI	-
Hotel Tineretului **	90 LEI	120 LEI	-

Train Station Phone: 0265/236284

Airport Phone: 0265/328258

Bus Station Phone: 0265/237774

Cab Companies: 0265/204948; 0265/204941

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